

COREQ Checklist (Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research)

The following checklist documents how this qualitative study meets the COREQ reporting guidelines. Each item is followed by a brief explanation or page reference indicating where the information can be found in the manuscript.

Domain 1: Research Team and Reflexivity

1. **Interviewer/facilitator** – The identity and role of the interviewer are described in the Methods section.
2. **Credentials** – The researchers' qualifications and professional backgrounds are detailed in the Author Contributions section.
3. **Occupation** – Current roles of the interviewers are mentioned in the Methods section.
4. **Gender** – Gender of the researchers is not considered relevant for the study and is not disclosed.
5. **Experience and training** – The training and experience of the interviewers in qualitative methods are described in the Methods section.

Domain 2: Study Design

6. **Methodological orientation** – The study uses a qualitative comparative design, described in the Methods section.
7. **Sampling** – Purposive sampling was used to select stakeholders for interviews.
8. **Method of approach** – Participants were recruited via professional contacts and email invitations.
9. **Sample size** – Twelve stakeholders were interviewed; this is stated in the Methods section.
10. **Non-participation** – All invited participants agreed to be interviewed.

Domain 3: Data Collection

11. **Setting** – Interviews were conducted via video conference or telephone; the setting is described in the Methods section.
12. **Presence of non-participants** – Interviews were conducted one-on-one; no other persons were present.
13. **Description of sample** – Participant roles and affiliations are summarized in the Methods and Discussion.
14. **Interview guide** – A semi-structured interview guide was used; it is provided as extended data.
15. **Audio/visual recording** – Interviews were audio-recorded with consent; this is mentioned in the Ethical considerations.
16. **Field notes** – The interviewer took notes during and after the interviews; this is documented in the Methods.

17. **Duration** – Interviews lasted approximately 30–60 minutes; stated in the Methods section.
18. **Data saturation** – Interviews continued until thematic saturation was achieved, as noted in the Methods.

Domain 4: Data Analysis and Reporting

19. **Number of data coders** – Two researchers independently coded the data, as described in the Methods.
20. **Description of the coding tree** – The coding framework and themes are explained in the Methods.
21. **Derivation of themes** – Themes were derived inductively from the data and described in the Analysis subsection.
22. **Software** – No specific qualitative analysis software was used; manual coding was performed.
23. **Participant checking** – Transcripts were not returned to participants for comment due to confidentiality considerations.
24. **Quotations presented** – Direct quotes from participants are included in the Results section with anonymized identifiers.
25. **Data and findings consistency** – The findings are supported by quotes from the transcripts.
26. **Clarity of major themes** – Major themes are clearly identified and described in the Results.
27. **Clarity of minor themes** – Minor themes are discussed in the Results, where relevant.

Each item above corresponds to a criterion in the COREQ checklist, and the explanations indicate how the study meets each criterion.